

A Comparative Study of 0.75% Ropivacaine with 0.5mcg/Kg Dexmedetomidine and 0.75% Ropivacaine with Normal Saline in Lower Abdominal and Lower Limb Surgeries by Epidural Route

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Abstract:

Introduction: Epidural anaesthesia gives adequate surgical anaesthesia, longer postoperative analgesia with minimal hemodynamic changes. Ropivacaine is suitable local anaesthetic drug. With Dexmedetomidine the anaesthetic and analgesic requirements get reduced because of its analgesic properties and increase of local anaesthetic effects.

Aim: To compare the sensory and motor blocking effects of epidurally administered 0.75 percent Ropivacaine using Dexmedetomidine and 0.75 percent Ropivacaine with normal saline in lower abdomen and lower limb procedures.

Materials and Methods: Sixty individuals of ASA classes I and II, ranging in age from 18 to 65 years, were allocated into two groups randomly with 30 patients. The epidural space was identified, an epidural catheter was inserted, study drug was given. The beginning of sensory block, the beginning of motor block, the maximal sensory level attained, the length of sensory block, the length of motor blockade, vital parameters were recorded.

Results: The Ropivacaine Dexmedetomidine group had a faster sensory onset than the Ropivacaine Normal saline group (5.70 ± 1.26 min vs 9.73 ± 1.64 min), ($p < 0.001$). The Ropivacaine Dexmedetomidine group had motor block onset earlier than the Ropivacaine Normal saline group (10.57 ± 1.52 min vs 13.90 ± 2.02 min), ($p < 0.001$). T6 in the Ropivacaine Normal saline group and T4 in the Ropivacaine Dexmedetomidine group were maximum sensory level ($p < 0.001$). Ropivacaine Dexmedetomidine group had a motor block intensity of 4, whereas Ropivacaine Normal saline group had a motor block intensity of 3 ($p < 0.001$). Ropivacaine Dexmedetomidine group had a longer sensory block duration than the Ropivacaine Normal saline group (366.67 ± 35.07 min vs 186.17 ± 7.84 min), ($p < 0.001$). Ropivacaine Dexmedetomidine group had a longer motor block duration than the Ropivacaine Normal saline group (262.33 ± 29.21 min vs 148.83 ± 5.97 min), ($p < 0.001$). Ropivacaine Dexmedetomidine group had higher sedation scores than the Ropivacaine with Normal saline group (4 vs 3), ($p < 0.001$). There was no significant variation in the hemodynamic parameters and the side effects reported were minimal.

Conclusion: It can be concluded that Ropivacaine plus Dexmedetomidine causes sensory and motor block more quickly, had longer sensory and motor block duration than Ropivacaine with Normal saline. Ropivacaine plus Dexmedetomidine also induced a stronger motor blockade and is higher on sedation than Ropivacaine with Normal saline with minimal side effects.

Keywords: Epidural, Ropivacaine, Dexmedetomidine.

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Introduction

The use of epidural anesthesia for lower abdomen and lower extremity procedures has expanded quickly in recent decades. However, sub-arachnoid anaesthesia, has some limitations, [1] like short

duration, the anaesthesia cannot be extended, fast onset of sympathetic blockade, less postoperative analgesia, and headache. The uses of epidural anaesthesia are that [2] it gives adequate surgical an-

aesthesia and can provide the longer duration of surgical needs, longer postoperative analgesia, reduces the occurrence of hemodynamic changes.

For epidural anaesthesia, a variety of local anaesthetics are employed [3], like Lignocaine and Bupivacaine. However, the disadvantage of lignocaine is medium duration activity. The problem of Bupivacaine is that it has a higher risk of cardiac toxicity if it is accidentally injected into the bloodstream. [4] Ropivacaine is new long-acting local anaesthetics that has a wider safety, offers all of the benefits of Bupivacaine [4] with low cardiovascular toxicity, [5] and has been proved to be an efficacious local anaesthetic for epidural anaesthesia in several studies. [6,7,8,9]

When administered directly to a single vagus nerve preparation, Richard et al. [10] discovered that Ropivacaine was less powerful than Bupivacaine in regard of transmission blockade of A β fibres. Ropivacaine inhibited A δ and C fibres more effectively than Bupivacaine. It's also worth noting that Ropivacaine has a lipid solubility of 2.9. [11]. As a result, Ropivacaine was chosen for present study. With local anaesthetics adjuvants of several kinds are employed. Stable vital parameters, good sedation, an ability to provide best postoperative analgesia are the main prudent qualities of an adjuvant.

Dexmedetomidine is a selective α_2 adrenergic agonist. By using Dexmedetomidine the anaesthetic and analgesic requirements get reduced because of its analgesic properties and increase of local anaesthetic effects. In addition, they cause altered transmembrane potential and ion conductance at locus ceruleus in the brainstem [12]. It has enhanced sympathoadrenal stability leading to decreased oxygen demand.

Aim:

To compare 0.75 percent Ropivacaine plus Dexmedetomidine and 0.75 percent Ropivacaine with Normal saline in lower abdomen and lower extremity surgeries, to evaluate the effect of adding Dexmedetomidine to Ropivacaine 0.75 percent in epidural lower abdomen and lower extremity procedures, concerning, Sensory block onset and duration, Motor block onset and duration, Attainment of Maximum sensory level, Motor blockade Intensity, Hemodynamic changes, Sedation score and Side effects

Material and Methods

A Randomized Double Blinded Control Study of 0.75 percent Ropivacaine with 0.5 mcg/kg Dexmedetomidine and 0.75 percent Ropivacaine with Normal saline in Lower Abdominal and Lower Limb Surgeries by Epidural Route, was carried out in 60 patients between 18-65 years, listed for elective lower abdomen and lower extremities surgical procedures, at Government Medical College, Sri-

kakulam, from May 2022-May 2024, with Institutional Ethics Committee acceptance and written informed consent from the patients. Blinding was achieved by making total volume to 16 ml in both groups. Resident who was preparing the study drug was not involved in the study.

The sample size calculation was done from Meitej AJ et al. [13] The average standard deviation was taken as 3.126 in group I and 3.908 in group II. To get 95% power and 95% confidence interval level and to detect a mean difference of 3.48 as statistically significant, we will need 27 subjects in each category. So, a sample size of 30 subjects in each group has been taken.

Subjects in this study were randomly categorized to 2 groups using computer-generated randomization numbers. There are 30 patients in each group.

- **Group I (n=30)** - 15ml of 0.75 percent Ropivacaine + 1ml Normal saline.
- **Group II (n=30)** -15ml of 0.75 percent Ropivacaine + 0.5 mcg/kg Dexmedetomidine (13)

Inclusion Criteria: People of both sexes between the ages of 18 and 65, ASA class I and II patients planned for elective lower abdomen and lower extremities surgeries.

Exclusion Criteria: Patient rejection for regional anaesthesia, Pregnancy and lactating individuals, Patients scheduled for Emergency surgeries, BMI > 30, Individuals having severe hypovolemia, bleeding coagulopathy, local infection, uncontrolled hypertension/ diabetes mellitus, neurological disorder and spine deformities, cardiovascular disease, liver disease, allergies are excluded from the study.

A routine pre-anesthetic assessment was done. On the night before surgery, alprazolam 0.5 mg tablet was given orally at bedtime. From 10 p.m. the day before surgery, kept nil by mouth. The patient's resting heart rate and blood pressure were measured on the day of operation. 30 minutes before the epidural procedure, preloaded with 500 ml Ringer lactate. Multi parameter monitor, which tracks Heart Rate (HR), oxygen saturation (SPO₂), Non-invasive Blood Pressure (NIBP) and continuous ECG monitoring was connected.

Under aseptic precautions, at L2-3 or L3-4 interspinous level with the patient's sitting position, entered the epidural space using an 18G Tuohy needle by the loss of resistance technique to air and epidural catheter was threaded and fixed. After aspiration, a test dose of 3 ml of 2 percent lignocaine with adrenaline is administered.

The commencement time was taken after the study drug was injected. At the conclusion of each minute, motor and sensory blocks were assessed and the start time for sensory and motor block, attainment of the maximal level, motor block intensity

and sedation levels were recorded. With 22 gauge needle sensory blockade was assessed at each level.

By using a modified Bromage scale, motor blockade was assessed in the lowerlimbs.

- Grade 0 – able to perform a full straight leg raise for 5 sec
- Grade 1– unable to perform the leg raise but can flex the knee
- Grade 2 – unable to flex the knee but can flex the ankle
- Grade 3 – unable to flex ankle but can move the toes
- Grade 4 – unable to move toes.

The level of sedation was assessed 10 min after grade 3 motor blockades and at the end of surgery based on the Ramsay sedation scale.

Vital signs like heart rate, blood pressure and saturation were measured each 5 minutes during the first hour, then each 15 minutes until the procedure was completed.

Intraoperative complications such as a change in heart rate, drop in pressure were observed, treated, and recorded. Hypotension is described as a drop in SBP of greater than 30 percent from baseline or an SBP of less than 90 mmHg. It's managed with more intravenous fluids and, injections of mephentermine 6 mg (I.V). Atropine 0.6 mg was

used to treat bradycardia (60 beats per minute) (I.V). If the patient reports of discomfort, an additional 8ml of 0.2 percent inj. Ropivacaine was given. Any unpleasant side effects, such as nausea, vomiting, dry mouth, shivering, and so on, were recorded.

The sensory block onset was taken from completing the study drug injection till sensation loss at T10 level.

The motor block onset was taken from completing the study drug injection until the patient develops grade 1 block of modified Bromage scale. The motor block duration was taken from the injection time to attainment of complete motor recovery (Bromage 0).

The sensory block duration was time taken from the injection until the patient reports pain at the T10 dermatomal level.

The current study's findings were statistically compared between the two groups. MS-EXCEL was used to enter data, and SPSS V25 was used to analyze it. Descriptive data with frequencies and percentages were represented. The association was determined by independent t-tests, Chi-square tests, and Fisher Exact tests. Statistical significance was described as a value.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Variables

	Group I	Group II	p value
Age (years)	48.60±9.7	46.10±9.0	>0.05
Gender (Male: Female)	21:9	22:8	>0.05
Height (cms)	165.8 ±9.0	164.9 ± 8.5	>0.05
Weight (Kgs)	59.77 ± 4.12	58.67 ± 4.29	>0.05
Mean Duration of Surgery (mins)	112.33 ± 15.18	112.17 ± 15.29	>0.05

Table 2: Meantime for the sensory onset (minutes)

Variable	Group	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	P- value
SensoryOnset (Min)	Group-I	30	5	12	9.73	1.64	<0.001
	Group-II	30	4	9	5.70	1.26	

Figure 1: Meantime for the sensory onset (minutes)

Table 3: Meantime for motor onset (minutes)

Variable	Group	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	P- Value
Motor Onset(Min)	Group-I	30	8	20	13.90	2.02	<0.001
	Group-II	30	9	15	10.57	1.52	

Figure 2: Meantime for motor onset (minutes)

Figure 3: Maximum dermatomal level attained

Figure 4: Motor Blockade Intensity

There is increased intensity motor blockade of Bromage 4 was found in patients in group II compared to group I, with significant p-value <0.001.

Figure 5: Sedation score

Dexmedetomidine group had more excellent scores compared to Ropivacaine group with a significant variation ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 6: Sensory block Duration (minutes)

The mean sensory block duration is 186.17 ± 7.84 mins in group I and 366.67 ± 35.07 mins in group II, and there is a statistically more significant variation between the groups ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 7: Motor Block Duration (minutes)

Mean duration of motor blockade is 148.83 ± 5.97 min in group I and 262.33 ± 29.21 min in group II with a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 8: Mean heart rate (bpm) at different time intervals

No significant variation in the mean heartrate was found between groups at various intervals.

Figure 9: Mean blood pressure (mmHg) at different time intervals

Table 4: Side Effects

Side Effects	Group-I		Group-II		P-value
	Count	%	Count	%	
Bradycardia	1	3.3%	4	13.3%	0.35
Hypotension	2	6.7%	6	20.0%	0.25
Nausea&vomiting	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	-
Shivering	1	3.3%	0	0%	1
Dry mouth	0	0%	1	3.3%	1

No statistically significant variation in side effects in both groups.

Discussion

Epidural anesthesia is considered as a gold standard technique as it provides complete and dynamic anesthesia. The benefits include suppression of stress response by sympatholysis, stable hemodynamics with reduction in cardiac morbidity, reduction in pulmonary complications due to active physiotherapy and early mobilization, reduced blood loss and decrease in thromboembolic complications following surgery.

Drugs chosen: Ropivacaine and Dexmedetomidine were chosen as the medications. Epidural anaesthesia with Ropivacaine was frequently used for lower extremity operations. Dexmedetomidine has been examined as a supplement to epidural local anaesthetic by a lot of authors. [13,14,15] As a result, Ropivacaine with Dexmedetomidine was used for this research.

Drugs Concentration selected: The drug's lipid solubility is related to its efficacy of local anaesthetic. Because Ropivacaine has a lesser lipid solubility than Bupivacaine, it is more likely to cause a significant differential motor and sensory block. [16] In their study, Casati et al. [17] found that patients given 0.5 percent Ropivacaine had a higher rate of insufficient motor block throughout operation than all those administered Bupivacaine. As a result, 0.75 percent Ropivacaine was chosen. The dexmedetomidine dose used in this trial was 0.5 mg/kg.

The pharmacological dose that has been chosen: The total volume required for inguinal hernioplasty and lower limb surgeries was 18 ml that was calculated as 1 ml /segment up to 150 cms of height and adding 0.1 ml /segment for every 5 cms of increasing height. [2]

With the mean height in both groups being 170 cms, and block up to T10 is needed for inguinal hernioplasty and lower extremity surgeries, the overall amount needed was 18 ml. As a result, 15 ml was chosen as the amount of the study medication excluding the test dose in both groups.

Casati et al. [17] evaluated Bupivacaine and Ropivacaine and employed graded epidural in their study for hip replacement surgery and found that 15 ml of Ropivacaine and 14 ml of Bupivacaine is the volume required to produce T10 level that was the same as in present study.

Demographic profile: There was no significant disparity in age, sex, weight, and height in between two categories, as per demographic statistics.

Sensory block onset: The time taken for sensory analgesia to start at T10 is 9.73 ± 1.64 minutes in Ropivacaine with Normal saline group and $5.7 \pm$

1.26 minutes in Ropivacaine with Dexmedetomidine group. This was significant statistically ($p < 0.001$). Suneeta Dutta, et al [14] found that the start of sensory analgesia was 9.06 ± 1.16 minutes in the Ropivacaine group and 5.14 ± 1.24 minutes in the Ropivacaine plus dexmedetomidine group, which matches with present study.

Surendra Kumar, Pravina [15] discovered that the period to acquire a sensory level at T10 in Group Ropivacaine+Dedmedetomidine (9.22 ± 0.86 min) was substantially less ($p < 0.001$) than in Ropivacaine+Fentanyl Group (11.30 ± 0.99 min), which was relevant to the present study.

The start of sensory analgesia at T10 in the Ropivacaine + dexmedetomidine group was 7.12 ± 2.44 minutes against 9.14 ± 2.94 minutes in the Ropivacaine +Fentanyl group, according to Bajwa SJ, Arora V et al. [18], which was statistically relevant and comparable to this study.

Maximum sensory level: The maximal sensory block level achieved in this study was T4 in the Ropivacaine with Dexmedetomidine group and T6 in the Ropivacaine with Normal saline group. The range of blocks in both categories, however, was extensive (T8- T4). Bajwa SJ, Arora V, et al. [18] found that the maximal level of sensory block attainment in Dexmedetomidine group was T4-6, contrasted to T5-T7 in group Fentanyl, which matches present findings. Bajwa SJ, Bajwa SK, Kaur J et al. [19] found that the maximal sensory level in Ropivacaine+ Dexmedetomidine group was T5-6 comparable to T6-T7 in Control group, which was consistent with present study.

Sensory block duration: The sensory block duration was determined to be longer in the Ropivacaine+ Dexmedetomidine category than in the Ropivacaine + Normal saline category. The Ropivacaine + Dexmedetomidine category had taken 366.67 ± 35.07 minutes, while the Ropivacaine + Normal saline category took 186.17 ± 7.84 minutes. It was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Suneeta Dutta et al [14] found a statistically significant discrepancy ($P < 0.0001$) in the sensory block length in the Ropivacaine group (216.61 ± 24.09 min) and the Ropivacaine and dexmedetomidine group (376.93 ± 35.56 min) which matches with this study. These results are in accordance with those of Bajwa SJ et al. [18], who found that the average time of analgesia in Dexmedetomidine group was 366.62 ± 24.42 minutes compared to 242.16 ± 23.86 minutes in Fentanyl group, which was extremely significant.

Motor block onset: The average time for motor block onset in the Ropivacaine plus Normal saline group was 13.90 ± 2.02 minutes, compared to

10.57 ± 1.52 minutes in the Ropivacaine plus Dexmedetomidine group, which was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Suneeta Dutta et al [14] found that the mean start of motor analgesia was 15.51 ± 1.78 minutes in the Ropivacaine group and 8.36 ± 1.74 minutes with in Ropivacaine plus Dexmedetomidine group, was also extremely significant. Surendra Kumar, Pravina [15] found that Group RD (10.12 min) had an earlier motor block onset than Group RF (13.36 min), with a significant variation ($p < 0.001$), this was consistent with existing study.

Motor block degree: In this study, it was determined that Ropivacaine with Dexmedetomidine group had a stronger motor block than Ropivacaine with Normal saline group. 21 patients in the Ropivacaine with Dexmedetomidine group had motor block of grade 4 compared with 2 subjects in Ropivacaine group. In addition, 7 patients in the Ropivacaine plus Normal saline group experienced grade 2 motor block, whereas none in Ropivacaine with Dexmedetomidine group did. This was statistically relevant ($p < 0.001$).

Suneeta Dutta, et al [14] found more potent motor inhibition of Bromage 4 in Dexmedetomidine individuals as compared to Ropivacaine individuals with a very significant p-value of 0.0001, which matches with this study.

Motor block duration: In Ropivacaine with Dexmedetomidine category, the motor block lasts 262.33 ± 29.21 minutes, whereas in Ropivacaine with Normal saline group, it lasts 148.83 ± 5.97 minutes which was considerably longer ($p < 0.001$).

Surendra Kumar, Pravina [15] in a comparable study reported that the length of motor block for Ropivacaine Dexmedetomidine Group was 231.88 ± 10.46 minutes and 209 ± 9.24 minutes in Ropivacaine Fentanyl Group, which was considerably greater ($p < 0.001$).

Suneeta Dutta et al [14] found that the average motor block duration was 151.51 ± 11.18 minutes in the Ropivacaine group and 201.16 ± 6.25 minutes in the Ropivacaine with Dexmedetomidine group, with a significant variation ($p = 0.0001$), which was comparable to this study.

Heart rate Variation: At different time intervals, there's no significant disparity in heart rate between the two categories. Four patients in Ropivacaine with Dexmedetomidine group and one in Ropivacaine with Normal saline group, developed bradycardia and were given inj. atropine 0.6mg. Similar to this study, Suneeta Dutta et al [14] observed no significant variation in average heart rate between two categories at varying times.

Blood pressure: SBP, DBP, and MAP measured at various intervals show no significant difference

statistically between the two groups. Six patients in Ropivacaine with Dexmedetomidine group and two in Ropivacaine with Normal saline group, on the other hand, had hypotension, which was treated with intravenous fluids and mephentermine injection.

According to Suneeta Dutta et al [14] there's no statistically significant variability in mean arterial pressure between the two categories.

Sedation score: The highest sedation score was 2 in the Ropivacaine plus Normal saline group, and 4 in the Ropivacaine plus Dexmedetomidine group ($p = 0.001$). This was statistically significant. Meitei AJ et al. [13] found that during the intraoperative time, the sedation level in Ropivacaine Dexmedetomidine Group was higher than in Ropivacaine Group, with a difference that was statistically significant which matches this study.

Surendra Kumar, Pravina, [15] reported that sedation point 2 was identified in a considerably higher proportion of patients from Ropivacaine Fentanyl Group (88 percent) than Ropivacaine Dexmedetomidine Group (6 percent). However, in most cases, the sedation level in Ropivacaine Dexmedetomidine Group was 4, which was similar to present findings

Side effects: Four patients in the Ropivacaine with Dexmedetomidine group developed bradycardia, while one patient in the Ropivacaine with Normal saline group developed bradycardia and was treated with inj. atropine. Significant hypotension was seen in six patients in the Ropivacaine with Dexmedetomidine group and two patients in the Ropivacaine with Normal saline group, both of whom were treated with intravenous fluids and inj. Mephentermine. Furthermore, one patient in the Ropivacaine with Normal saline group showed shivering and was treated with Inj. Tramadol. One patient in Ropivacaine with Dexmedetomidine group had dry mouth. In both groups, no one had nausea or vomiting. There was no statistical significance between two groups. These correlated with the findings of Suneeta Dutta et al [14].

Study Limitations: The sample size was modest in this single-center study, the serum concentrations of Dexmedetomidine could not be measured, the level of sedation was assessed using a sedation scale rather than a Bispectral Index monitor.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that Ropivacaine plus Dexmedetomidine causes sensory and motor block more quickly and also had longer sensory and motor block duration than Ropivacaine with Normal saline. Ropivacaine plus Dexmedetomidine also induced a stronger motor blockade and is higher on sedation than Ropivacaine with Normal saline with minimal side effects.

Hence, Epidural Dexmedetomidine combined with Ropivacaine had the synergistic effects and can be an advantageous adjuvant to Ropivacaine for lower abdominal and lower extremity surgeries by epidural route.

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